

To whom it may concern:

I started working with Afonso Willian Nunes in 2021 on the application of Lie symmetries to find exact solutions for some non-uniform rod models. As a result of the research carried out, we were able to publish a paper in the prestigious *Journal of Sound and Vibration*. He also carried out a research stay at the University of Cádiz under my supervision in the period 6/05/24 to 26/05/24. During this stay we worked together on the determination of new solutions of the travelling wave type to a generalised Calogero-Bogoyavlenskii-Schiff partial differential equation.

Afonso Willian is very hardworking and always open to learning new mathematical topics. He is very careful with his work and always tries to understand the underlying theory. During his research stay, he was also able to make contacts with other PhD students from the University of Cádiz, so he is always ready to work in collaboration teams.

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